

Kinetics of the Hydrolysis of Tri-2,4-Dichlorophenyl Phosphate

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Kinetics of the hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate has been investigated in aqueous-dioxan medium at 98°, in buffers of pH 1.24 to 7.46 and in acidic solutions. The ester was found to hydrolyse via conjugate acid species. pH-log rate profile shows that there is linear increase in rates with acidity and attains optimum value in 2.5M hydrochloric acid. Reactivity of the ester in buffer solutions decreases considerably than in acidic medium. Conjugate acid species of the ester have been shown to be the only species undergoing negative salt effect, while inert neutral species remains unaffected. Theoretical rates determined from ionic strength data agree well with the experimentally observed rates. Solvent effect and solvent isotope effect have been studied.

THE survey^{1,2,3} of literature of hydrolysis of triesters shows that very little kinetic study has been carried out. The recent biochemical researches⁴ have immensely increased the importance of phosphoric acid derivatives and the role of phosphate linkages involved in biochemical changes. To help in the understanding of the problem of the complicated biochemical reactions, kinetics of the hydrolysis of substituted tri-benzyl⁵, triaryl⁶ and triallyl⁷ esters of phosphoric acid have been studied in this school. Investigation of the study of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate which is a flame-resistant plasticizer⁸ and defoliating and desiccating agent⁹ for cotton is undertaken to find out whether the chlorine atoms in ortho and para position of the phosphate bring about any variation in reaction pathway in addition to change in the rate.

Materials and Methods

Tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate was prepared from 2,4-dichlorophenol by phosphorus pentachloride method^{10,11}, and was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 94°-95° (Found: C, 40.86; H, 1.80; P, 5.92; requires C, 40.56; H, 1.70; P, 5.81),

Procedure

The hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate ($5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$, unless otherwise specified) has been investigated in aqueous-dioxan medium (dioxan-water: 50:50 V/V) at $98 \pm 0.05^\circ$ by performing runs in buffer solutions ranging from pH 1.24 to 7.46 and in acidic solution ranging from 0.1 to 4.5 M hydrochloric acid. The rate constants were determined by estimating inorganic phosphate colorimetrically by Allen's method.¹² The hydrolytic reactions of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate in acid solutions and in some buffer solutions are not isolated reactions, therefore the rate of each reaction has been correctly

calculated by mirror method^{13,14}. Constant ionic strength¹³ was maintained using mixtures of sodium chloride and hydrochloric acid. Interpolated values of buffers at 98° determined from the work of Stene¹⁵ were used. Deuterium oxide (B.A.R.C., Trombay) was of 99.4% of isotopic purity. Dioxan was purified¹⁶. All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. (A.R.) and Riedel quality.

Results and Discussion

pH log rate profile (Fig. 1) for the hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 98°, shows that

Fig. 1. pH-log rate profile for the hydrolysis of Tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 98°. k_e —Rate constant.

in the region pH 2.0 to 4.5 M hydrochloric acid, the pseudo-first order rate coefficients increase with the increase in acidity upto 2.5 M hydrochloric acid and beyond this acidity the rate coefficients decrease. Unlike benzyl phosphate⁵, this ester shows bend in strong acid solution. Such a maximum has been observed in hydrolysis of substituted triphenyl phosphates⁶ and it was explained on the basis of complete conversion of substrate into its conjugate acid species. In this case decrease in rate beyond 2.5 M hydrochloric acid, is probably due to ionic strength effect as observed in case of ϵ -caprolactam¹⁷. Profile of pH versus log rate shows constancy of rates

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in the region pH 2.0 to 4.0 and then there is a slight decrease upto pH 7.46. Such changes in the rate constants in this region may be presumed to be due to decrease in concentration of conjugate acid species and formation of inert neutral species. Kinetic data at constant ionic strength (Table 1) indicate acid catalysis. As has been done for the

TABLE 1—RATES OF HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-2; 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH

HCl (M)	$10^3 k_e$ (min. ⁻¹)
	$\mu = 1.0$
0.1	0.60
0.3	1.72
0.5	2.65
0.7	3.59
1.0	5.26
	$\mu = 1.5$
0.5	2.12
0.8	3.38
1.0	4.20
1.2	5.10
1.5	6.39
	$\mu = 2.0$
1.0	3.24
1.3	4.49
1.5	5.19
1.7	6.01
2.0	7.00

hydrolysis of dimethyl phosphate^{3,13}, the rate constants were plotted against acidities (Fig. 2), at constant ionic strength. Fig. 2 indicates that the linear curves meet at origin with slopes (k_{H^+} , specific acid catalysed rates) of decreasing order with the

Fig. 2. Acid hydrolysis of Tri-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at constant ionic strength, temperature 98°C. k_e — Rate constant.

increase of ionic strength. This suggests negligible contribution from hydrolysis via neutral species to the acid catalysed reaction, in the overall range studied. The conjugate acid species is found to be the only species susceptible to ionic strength effect giving negative salt effect while the inert neutral species remains unaffected. Similar behaviour has been observed for hydrolysis of lactams¹⁷. Linearity

of the curve (Fig. 2) proves the validity of the modified form of Bronsted-Bjerrum¹⁸ equation. The observed acid-catalysed rate coefficient (k_e), determined from Bronsted-Bjerrum equation for the conventional reaction scheme :

(where S, is phosphate, and $X^\ddagger$, is the transition complex) may be represented as,

$$k_e = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = k_{H_3O^+} \cdot C_{H_3O^+} \cdot C_{H_2O} \frac{f_S \cdot f_{H_2O} \cdot f_{H^+}}{f_{X^\ddagger}} \dots \quad (i)$$

(where the symbols k , C and f have customary significance).

Since activity coefficient term varies logarithmically with ionic strength and C_{H_2O} kinetically remains constant, equation (i) becomes,

$$\log k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = \log k_{H_3O^+} + \log C_{H^+} - b'_{H^+} \mu$$

$$\log k_{H^+} = \log k_{H_3O^+} - b'_{H^+} \mu$$

where $\log k_{H_3O^+}$ (specific acid catalysed rate at zero ionic strength) and b'_{H^+} (constant), are the intercepts on rate axis and slope respectively, of the linear plot between ionic strengths and $\log k_{H^+}$.

The overall rate of the reaction has been estimated from the equation

$$k_{e(\text{ca.})} = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+}$$

The rates so estimated closely agree with experimentally observed rates (Table 2).

TABLE 2—CALCULATED AND OBSERVED RATES FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-2; 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 98°C.

HCl M	$10^3 k_{H^+} + (\text{min}^{-1})$	Calculated rates $10^3 k_e$ (min ⁻¹)	Observed rates $10^3 k_e$ (min ⁻¹)
0.01	8.30	0.083	0.08
0.05	8.14	0.410	0.40
0.10	7.97	0.797	0.68
0.50	6.70	3.35	3.06
1.00	5.39	5.39	5.26
1.50	4.34	6.51	6.39
2.00	3.50	7.00	7.00
2.50	2.82	7.05	7.42
3.00	2.27	6.81	6.42
3.50	1.82	6.37	5.77
4.00	1.47	5.88	6.51
4.50	1.18	5.31	4.99

Bimolecularity of the acid catalysed reaction in moderately strong acid solution has been supported, using Zücker-Hammett hypothesis¹⁹. The slope, 0.88 of the linear plot between log rate coefficients and log acidities (Fig. 3) which is nearly unity, confirms the bimolecular nature of the reaction. Slope slightly less than unity, is due to negative salt effect on acid catalysed rates.

Fig. 3. Zücker-Hammett plot for the hydrolysis of Tri-,2 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 98°. k_e —Rate constant.

Bimolecular nature of the reaction should result in high negative entropy of activation and comparatively small activation energy²⁰. Arrhenius parameters²⁰ for the hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate have been calculated, in 1.0 and 3.5 M hydrochloric acid, and in buffer medium of pH 3.33, (Table 3) at different temperatures 80°, 90° and 98°

TABLE 3—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-2, 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 98°

Medium	PARAMETERS		
	Energy of activation 'E' K.cal/mole.	Frequency factor 'A' sec. ⁻¹	Entropy $\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.
1.0 M HCl	17.5	2.15×10^6	-32.2
3.5 M HCl	15.5	1.62×10^5	-37.5
Buffer of pH 3.33	19.3	2.76×10^6	-36.0

for knowing the reaction mechanism on both sides of the maximum and also in buffer medium, and found to be of bimolecular range.

The theory of solvent effect put forward by Hughes and Ingold²¹ has been used for knowing the nature of transition state of the hydrolytic reaction in acid medium and in buffer medium. Decrease in rate with the increase in ionizing power of the solvent (Table 4) in 1.0 and 3.5 M hydrochloric acid and in buffer medium of pH 3.33, in case of the hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate, shows dispersion of the charge in the transition state. In acid medium on both sides of the maximum (Fig. 1), it is expected also, because probable reactive species in the region pH 2.0 to 4.5 M HCl is conjugate acid species, but in buffer solution of pH 3.33, it is unexpected because probable reactive species, expected in the region pH 2.0 to 7.46 is neutral species. Above results (Table 4) show that in this range also, conjugate acid species is reactive, but, its concentration is very less due to its conversion into inert neutral species. Ionic strength data also clearly indicate that, there is negligible contribution by neutral species (Fig. 2) to overall reaction rate.

Solvent isotope effect has been carried out in 1.0 M hydrochloric acid by change over from dioxan-water to dioxan-D₂O ($k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} = 0.71$), to understand the nature of proton transfer equilibrium and molecularity. Such lower rates in D₂O²² for specific acid catalysed reaction were taken to be due to the formation of rigid hydrogen bonded transition state, causing high negative value of entropy of activation and low activation energy (Table 3).

TABLE 4—THE INFLUENCE OF THE SOLVENT ON THE RATE OF HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-2, 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 98°

Percentage of dioxan (V/V)	40	50	60
$k_e \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$ (1.0 M HCl)	4.98	5.26	5.42
$k_e \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$ (3.5 M HCl)	5.50	5.77	6.25
$k_e \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$ (pH 3.33)	0.021	0.075	0.094

The ionic strength data confirms the negligible contribution of neutral species. The solvent effect shows the existence of conjugate acid species in the region pH 2.0 to 7.46. So it can be concluded that,

TABLE 5—COMPARATIVE KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF TRIPHENYL PHOSPHATE ESTERS VIA CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES

S. No.	Phosphate ester	Medium	E K.cal/mole	A (sec. ⁻¹)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Maxima
1.	Tri- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl. ⁶	1.0 M HClO ₄	13.73	7.4×10^3	-47.68	2
2.	Tri-2, 6-dimethoxy phenyl. ²³	4.0 M HCl	21.59	9.81×10^6	-19.19	—
3.	Tri-2, 4-dichloro phenyl	1.0 M HCl	17.5	2.15×10^6	-32.2	2.5
4.	Tri- <i>o</i> -methoxy- <i>p</i> -methyl phenyl. ²⁴	2.0 M HCl	11.4	2.6×10^5	-54.5	4

throughout the range, the hydrolytic reaction of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate, takes place via its conjugate acid species.

Phosphorus-oxygen bond fission of the conjugate acid species of the ester is expected to be more probable during hydrolysis due to the formation of resonance stabilised phenoxide ion. Such a P-O bond fission will be facilitated by the electron attracting chlorine substituents. The P-O bond fission is further indicated from the comparative kinetic data (Table 5). On the basis of experimental evidences the probable reaction paths for the hydrolysis of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate may be formulated as shown in Chart I. This is followed by the hydrolysis of diester¹⁴ into monoester¹⁴ and then into inorganic phosphate. If the graph is plotted between the energy of activations (E) and entropy of activations ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) of the different phosphates (Table 5), the point of tri-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate clearly lie close to the linear plot¹⁴ on which the points of other esters lie, supports the proposed mechanism shown in Chart I.

Chart I. Mechanism for the hydrolysis of Tri-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate via its conjugate acid species.

References

1. C. A. VERNON, Special Publication No. 8. The Chem. Soc., London, 1957, p. 17.
2. P. W. C. BARNARD, C. A., BUNTON, D. R. LLEWELLYN, C. A. VERNON and V. A. WELCH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2670.
3. J. R. COX (Jr.) and O. B. RAMSAY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 64, 317.
4. H. G. KHORANA, "Some Recent Developments in Chemistry of Phosphate Esters of Biological Interest", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1961.
5. V. M. KAWADIKAR, "Kinetics of the Reactions of Some *p*-Substituted Benzyl Phosphates", Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1970.
6. G. KASTURI (MRS.), "Nucleophilic Substitution in Some Organic Phosphates", Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1969.
7. S. B. SAXENA, "Studies in C-O-P Linkage of Some Organo Phosphorus Compounds", Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, Gwalior 1968.
8. G. KAMAI and A. P. BAGDANOV, *Trudy Kazan, Khim-Tekhnol. Inst. im S. M. Kirova*, 1953, 18, 22.
9. CHEM ABS, 1969, 70, 105368Z.
10. A. D. ST. JOHN, U.S. Pat. 1, 1923, 462, 306.
11. R. L. SHUMAN, U.S. Pat. 2, 1938, 133, 310.
12. R. J. L. ALLEN, *Biochem. J.*, 1940, 34, 858.
13. C. A. BUNTON, M. M. MHALA, K. G. OLDHAM and C. A. VERNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3293.
14. S. S. BHATAWDEKAR, "2, 4-Dichlorophenyl Phosphate Esters—A Hydrolytic Study", Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, Gwalior, 1972.
15. S. STENE, *Recl. Trav. Chim., Pays-Bas Belg.*, 1930, 49, 1133.
16. K. HESS and H. FRAHM, *Br. dt. Chem. Ges.*, 1938, 71, 2627.
17. M. M. MHALA and M. H. JAGDALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 711.
18. F. A. LONG and W. F. C. DEVIT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 51, 119.
19. L. ZUCKER and L. P. HAMMETT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2791.
20. L. L. SCHALEGER and F. A. LONG, "Advances in Physical Organic Chemistry", Vol. 1, (Ed) V. Gold, Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1963, p. 26.
21. E. D. HUGHES and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 244.
22. P. W. C. BARNARD, C. A. BUNTON, D. KELLERMAN, M. M. MHALA, B. L. SILVER, C. A. VERNON and V. A. WELCH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, Sec. B, 227.
23. M. M. MHALA and SHASHI PRABHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 1073.
24. V. B. KADMANE, "Hydrolysis of 2-Methoxy, 4-Methyl Phenyl Phosphate". Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, Gwalior 1971.